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Interventions of drama-based training within corporate milieu: cases of two organizations in India

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Abstract:

Drama-based trainings are increasingly popular with corporate India in a variety of settings. The purpose of this paper is to highlight the use of such drama-based interventions and their impact on employees through cases of two organisations in India, one for inducing awareness and understanding of the brand proposition among employees and the other for educating them on safety protocols. It is difficult to achieve desired behavioural change or understanding when interventions are too theoretical or lack experientiality. Out-of-the-box thinking motivates organisations to venture beyond tried-and-true methods of employee training in order to experiment with novel approaches. Drama's dynamic nature encourages audience participation, either directly, as in a forum or interactive theatre, or indirectly, through observation, and assists the target audience in absorbing learnings through experience. This paper demonstrates the importance of making an impact through a novel and alternate mode of training as one through drama by detailing two cases of drama-based interventions being used in various areas of specialisation and how its usage has tremendous potential to achieve learning outcomes without making the process tedious for participants.

Keywords:

Drama-based Training, Learning & Development, Training, Theatre-based Training.

I. Introduction:

Creative drama, defined by the American Association of Theatre for Youth in 1978, is a non-exhibitional, process-centered theatre that encourages participants to imagine, enact, and reflect on the human experience. The essence of drama lies in its creative nature, with Jacob Moreno's psychodrama being one of its earliest formal uses. This form of drama-based intervention expanded to include employee relations and business training, with its use increasing in the 1960s and 1970s.

Google Scholar and Google search reveal a growing interest in drama-based interventions, which are expanding their scope from education to clinical experiments and are now rapidly moving to the corporate environment. These interventions are found in various disciplines, including education, medical education, and healthcare, law, and research, with numerous references from Wilkes (2008).

The United States and the United Kingdom dominate publications on drama-based training or theatre or arts-based trainings and/or interventions, as shown in Table. 1 by the graph depicting publication-wise leading countries in the said area. Turkey, Australia, and Finland

Beyond South Korea, the last on this list, the number of publications per country is negligible and thus not depicted in the graph.

Table.1: Country wise publications on areas related to drama-based training

Table. 2 lists the disciplines where drama is used as a training tool, with social sciences and medicine at the top. A Google search on drama-based training shows numerous companies specializing in this genre, conducting training programs for organizations in areas like communication, conflict resolution, change management, and gender sensitization.

Table.2: Disciplines in which drama/theater-based interventions are being used as a tool for training

India's learning and development industry, worth over US\$ 3.5 billion, is rapidly growing. Organizations like HAL and ITC are experimenting with new training methods, resulting in increased demand for experienced professionals. Theatre-based corporate trainings, such as diversity and legal implications training, have evolved in India. Companies like ITC and HAL have already incorporated drama-based programs into their employee training methodologies.

The knowledge-driven economy necessitates the evolution of existing learning and development methodologies. As Indian organizations expand, so does the need to invest in training programs to prepare employees for global competition. Novel and effective interventions are needed at every stage of a company's life cycle.

Two case studies in India reveal the effectiveness of drama-based interventions in achieving learning objectives. These studies, conducted with managers, reveal that employees demonstrated greater enthusiasm for learning through drama-based interventions than classroom sessions, highlighting the potential of such interventions in India.

Case 1: Assessing the gap between the existing & desired culture at strata capital for building brand proposition and bridging it through drama-based interventions:

Strata Capital, a Non-Banking Financial Services (NBFC) registered with the Reserve Bank of India, is a leading financial services venture established in 2007. The company faces challenges in the financial sector, which is dominated by entrenched players. Strata Capital aims to forge a distinct identity by leveraging the twin brand pillars of trust and credibility, which are strongly associated with the parent group. The company faces a decline in trust in the financial sector,

particularly banking, and potential misbehavior from big players. Strata Capital's management believes it can capitalize on the available white spaces in the industry.

The brand aimed to earn the trust and admiration of all stakeholders by combining genuine care with expertise to advise customers on the best products. This led to the birth of the company's brand proposition, which was crucial for internalizing brand values and developing employees' ability to translate brand identity to brand reality for customers and relevant stakeholders.

The Strata Capital Identity Survey, a repeated survey, aimed to gauge employees' perception and understanding of the brand proposition.

The survey was conducted online using e-mailers and Googledocs on the back end, an intranet login page, and a desktop medium for message reinforcement. The vast majority of employees (n= 254) enthusiastically participated.

It revealed a significant gap in employees' awareness and understanding of the brand proposition. Only 10% of respondents agreed that they understood what needed to be done and the behaviors that needed to be demonstrated in order to become customers' preferred financial services providers. 15% of respondents thought the brand proposition was unique and provided a good opportunity for Strata Capital to make its mark in the crowded BFSI sector.

70% of employees reported a lack of understanding of how to live the brand during critical moments with customers. Only 23% of respondents believed that the communication channels used to cascade the brand proposition internally were effective in fostering the desired behavioral changes. The company sought a creative approach to traditional communication methods, such as standard e-mailers and leadership messages, as employees felt they were passive and did not adequately engage with the brand promise. An interactive medium was developed for storytelling and behavioral change.

2. The birth of stage on - the strata capital theatre group:

Strata Capital's employee theatre group, Stage On, uses theatre and storytelling to address complex organizational issues. The Mumbai office, which accounts for 25% of the total employee base, is part of the pan-India presence, with auditions held to screen potential employees who can use improvisational skills. Stage On aims to foster peer-to-peer collaboration and communication.

Strata Capital's employee theatre group, Stage On, aimed to use theatre and storytelling to communicate complex organizational issues and foster peer-to-peer collaboration. The Mumbai branch successfully screened Stage On's in-house performances, leading to the formation of a group of 12 actors and actresses to represent the initiative. The company's Annual Day post featured Stage On, generating excitement and buzz, and rehearsals began soon after. The Mumbai branch's success showcases the power of theatre in fostering collaboration and understanding.

3. Framing techniques:

Strata Capital, a leading financial services company, has created a series of employee surveys to create frames that depict situations employees might face during difficult times. These frames were then demystified using intuitive scripting and storytelling, focusing on desired behavior for Strata Capital employees. Examples include selling to customers at the end of the month, explaining finer details, pacifying irate customers, caring for colleagues, and caring for society. The frames were then acted out on stage, with a *sutradhar* character representing the polar opposite of an ideal Strata Capital employee, and the remaining actors demonstrating the appropriate behavior for that frame.

Strata Capital conducted a survey on the complex aspect of Brand promise, focusing on the role of StageOn in guiding employees through daily dilemmas. The feedback was positive, with senior management team members praising the actors' performance. The Strata Capital identity survey revealed a positive shift in employee perception and comprehension of the Brand identity, indicating StageOn's role in guiding employees through their daily interactions with customers and stakeholders.

Case 2: Using drama-based interventions to get closer to the milestone of zero injuries at Sysik, India:

Sysik is an engineering firm that operates in the tooling, materials technology, mining, and construction industries. The lost time injury frequency rate (LTIFR) is a metric that many businesses use to report on safety. It's a key performance indicator (KPI) that shows the relationship between the numbers of hours worked and the number of lost time injuries (LTI). A "frequency rate" is used to ensure that businesses can be compared on equal footing. The frequency rate in this case is per million hours. Finally, the majority of LTIFRs are computed

over a 12-month period. This has the effect of "averaging out" any spikes or dips in hours or LTIs. As a result, the full LTIFR calculation is as follows:

$$(\text{Avg.}) \text{LTIFR} = \text{No. LTIs p.a.} / \text{Hours p.a.} \times 1,000,000.$$

The calculation above tells us how many serious injuries can be expected for each million hours worked.

4. A step closer to zero injuries:

Given the challenges and risks that the industries in which Sysik operates face (mining, roads, ports, oil rigs, automobile, and aviation manufacturing facilities), keeping a safe working environment has always been a top priority. To highlight the company's strong focus in this area, it established the "Zero Harm" vision and aimed to achieve it through globalization and localization. In other words, the company attempted to think globally while acting locally. This included finding ways to more efficiently coordinate and standardize various activities across business areas, as well as driving innovation. All aspects of the group's safety were integrated. Top management believed that it was critical to establish active and visible leadership, a knowledge-sharing corporate culture, strong communication, and consistent accountability in order to continue on the path to success.

5. Campaigns:

The company's health and safety strategy focused primarily on preventative measures and various activities to change the corporate culture. Several campaigns were carried out, primarily to raise awareness about the need to reduce the number of crush injuries in manufacturing operations. These campaigns, collectively known as the "Hands and Fingers" campaign, aided in raising awareness and, as a result, lowering the frequency of injuries. For mining equipment sales personnel at Sysik Mining, an extensive training programme known as "Speaking Safety" was initiated. Based on the Group's strong safety culture, this programme assisted sales personnel in feeling more comfortable communicating with customers about product safety solutions and viewing this as a sales advantage.

6. At Sysik India:

Despite a significant improvement in the reported lost time injury frequency rate (LTIFR), Sysik India's safety standards were a source of concern and scrutiny in some cases. Breach of safety protocols was reported in some quarters. Several campaigns were launched to raise employee awareness in this area. The goal was to establish an industry-leading safety culture and to instill it in customers and suppliers. However, the occurrences of various safety lapses indicated that much more work was required to fully instill a safety culture in the organization.

7. Using theatre to educate employees on self-security and workplace safety:

When the topic of drama-based safety campaigns was brought up in one of the Union meetings at Sysik India, it immediately drew the full support of union members and blue-collar workers. One of the senior members, with a strong track record of stage performance, agreed to serve as the initiative's main anchor.

Auditions were held, and a group of 20 enthusiastic actors were chosen to join the theatre group. The performance was scheduled to premiere on World Safety Day.

8. Setting the stage:

Sysik adhered to a strict safety protocol, which was well documented in a safety manual. A random dipstick test, however, revealed that employees were not fully aware of the protocols and procedures. Using the results of the employee survey, frames were created around specific safety areas. Scripting and storytelling came next. Each frame featured one actor breaking the safety protocol and the other actors educating him on the desired behaviour the employee should exhibit to protect himself/herself.

The on-stage interactions of the actors provided solutions to the safety dilemmas depicted in the frames. Sysik India reported an improvement in its LTIFR records as a result of this intervention, and it is now being considered for adoption as a best practise for global replication by Sysik's other business units.

9. Conclusion:

Drama-based interventions are becoming more popular in organizations, and they have found an audience in India as well. There are numerous professional players in this arena who assist

organizations in achieving their desired learning and behavioral change objectives. The distinction between the two cases is that in both, employees performed their theatrical roles with zeal without the assistance of a professional theatre group. The performance was well received by the target audience, which included other employees. In these cases, such interventions were an excellent tool for increasing employee engagement. Greater understanding and assimilation of such initiatives can create a win-win situation for both trainers and learners by ensuring both parties' engagement. It has the potential to significantly improve learning through entertainment by moving it beyond the lecture mode and into the realm of interaction and participation. This could have a significant impact on HRD managers and L&D professionals in organizations.

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